

RNR74802 (Sona/ Manoharsali) has long slender grains and RNR1535 (Tella Hamsa/ARC14302) has medium bold grains. They are now in minikit trials in A.P. □

Table 2. Average ShB scores, 1986 and 1987.

Cultivar	Disease score
RNR6250	4.3
RNR74802	4.5
RNR1535	4.8
RNR1-138-8-1	5.0
RNR1806	5.1
RNR18953	5.1
RNR98357	5.4
RNR9075	5.4
RNR133-87	5.4
RNR10244	5.5
RNR89128	5.6
RNR286	5.6
RNR3070	5.7
RNR9062	5.8
RNR99372	5.9
RNR1-111-63	5.9
RNR82096	6.0
RNR5 204	6.0
RNR15-97-36	6.0
RNR52147	6.1
RNR32341	6.1
RNR6827	6.2
RNR16210	6.5
RNR99514	6.6
RNR17085	6.7
RNR9139	6.8
RNR15-84-11	6.8
RNR769	6.8
RNR18586	6.8
RNR99378	6.8
RNR10212	6.9
RNR10208	6.9
RNR99180	7.1
RNR18545	7.1
RNR17-1864	7.1
RNR18864	7.1
RNR527	7.1
RNR16050	7.2
TN1 (check)	7.2
SE (m) ±	0.4

Field evaluation for resistance to rice grassy stunt virus (GSV)

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Severe yellowing and stunting affected rice in the Kuttanad area of Kerala, India, during 1988 kharif (Aug-Sep to Oct-Nov). Serological tests at the

Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, confirmed the presence of GSV strain 2 (GSV-2).

We screened 7 varieties, 8 prerelease cultivars from 3 crosses, and 70 promising cultivars from 16 crosses for resistance to GSV-2 in the field.

None of the seven varieties showed resistance (see table). Of the eight prerelease cultivars, only KAU168

(ARC6650/ Jaya) showed moderate resistance.

Twelve cultivars from the crosses MO 5/ Improved Sona, MO 4/ Culture 25331, Culture 1954/ Jyothi, Jyothi/ Culture 25331, Vykatharyan/ MO 6, Thonnooran/ IR8, and Thonnooran/ MO 6 showed moderate resistance. □

Varietal resistance to GSV strain 2. Kerala, India, 1988 kharif.

Variety or culture	Parentage	GSV-2 damage ^a (0-9)	Grain yield (t/ha)
MO 4 (Bhadra)		5	0.2
MO 5 (Asha (R))		5	1.0
MO 6 (Pavizham)		4	2.3
MO 7 (Karthika)		4	1.3
Jyothi		4	1.4
Mahaveera		4	0.9
Jaya		4	0.8
KAU93	Jaya/Ptb 33	4	1.1
KAU126	Jaya/Ptb 33	4	1.8
KAU129	Jaya/Ptb 33	4	1.6
KAU153-1	IR1561/Ptb 33	4	1.4
KAU168	ARC6650/Jaya	2	4.4
KAU170	ARC6650/Jaya	4	1.8
KAU200	IR1561/Ptb 33	4	2.0
KAU204	IR1561/Ptb 33	4	1.3
M28-1-1	MO 5/Improved Sona	3	1.4
M38-2-1-1	MO 4/Culture 25331	3	2.1
M38-2-1-2	MO 4/Culture 25331	3	1.3
M38-4-1	MO 4/Culture 25331	3	1.9
M38-8-2	MO 4/Culture 25331	3	3.1
M39-3-1	Culture 1954/Jyothi	3	1.7
M40-5-2	Jyothi/Culture 25331	3	1.5
M41-16-2	Vykatharyan/ MO 6	3	2.1
M48-11-1	Thonnooran/ IR8	3	1.4
M48-11-2	Thonnooran/ IR8	3	1.9
M48-11-3	Thonnooran/ IR8	3	2.9
M49-2-3	Thonnooran/ MO 6	3	1.6

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

Resistance of TKM6 and IR20 to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV)

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In the greenhouse, TKM6 and IR lines with TKM6 in their parentage show high levels of resistance to RTSV infection, but are susceptible to rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) infection. Field trials at the IRRI farm confirm the resistance of TKM6 and IR20 to RTSV.

In 1987 wet season (WS), TKM6 and TN1 planted in 25- × 50-m plots at 20- × 20-cm spacing were subjected to natural infection. Leaf samples were collected at 18, 32, 49, and 92 d after transplanting (DT) from a sample of 36 hills. Each plot had 10 sampling units arranged in a W-pattern.

In 1988 WS, IR20 (IR262-24-3/TKM6) was planted in 21- × 21-m plots at 20- × 20-cm spacing. Leaf samples were collected from a sample of 9 hills at 14, 28, 42, and 55 DT. The 46 sampling units/plot were arranged in a quincuncial pattern. Leaf samples were